

Sm@ll Ruminant Technologies

3D Imaging

Need: Automatic estimation of Body Condition Score (BCS)

Aim:

- Monitoring of animals' condition
- More regular and objective data

Description: A tool with 6 3D cameras can take a photo of the shape of part of the animal or the whole animal. The prototype is currently in the research phase, and algorithms are being created to estimate the weight and NEC of ewes. Other systems exist in other sectors.

How to Implement: The prototype is installed in a restraint corridor. The flow is managed by two gates, one at the entrance and one at the exit. The animal is identified as it passes through and an image is taken (automatically or by the operator). Images are taken quickly (a few tenths of a second). The images are then sorted automatically and an algorithm estimates the weight of the ewes. The estimation of Body Condition Score using 3D imagery is not yet robust and reliable.

Expected Benefits:

- Better animal monitoring
- Less stress for the animals and the farmer

Country:

France

Production System (dairy or/and meat sheep/goat):

Meat sheep

Category of Animal (ewe, goat, replacement, lamb, kid):

Ewes

Source of Information:

<https://idele.fr/Otop-3D/>

Attachment/links :
<http://idele.fr/reseaux-et-partenariats/otop3d/publication/idelesolr/recommends/otop-3d-les-dispositifs-dacquisitions-sont-prets.html>

Prerequisites and/or limits :

- Depends on the configuration of the restraint park
- Still in the test / prototype phase

Costs and Challenges

- Set up costs: 5 000 € - 15 000 €
- Subscription required: No
- Ease of use? Scale 1 (Complicated) – 10 (Simple)

- Value for money (for this type of benchmark farm)? Maybe
- Recommend this tool/technology for use on other types of farm? Yes

This technology is a prototype being tested on the French meat sheep Digifarm. It can be used to estimate the weight of animals using 3D images. Future objectives are to obtain other information such as body condition score, plumbness, etc.

FARMER FROM FRANCE

It would take 22 years for 72% adoption in Estonia.

www.smartplatform.network

Need:	Time management software.
Aim:	Know the distribution of the breeder's working time and analyze his organization
Description:	<p>Aptimiz is a solution for the automatic measurement of manual and mechanized working time considering the distribution by activity and by type of production.</p> <p>Thanks to geolocation, Aptimiz determines the work on which the breeder is working and records the time spent without any entry. Time can be analyzed by task, by area, by person, by machine, taking travel times into consideration. The web platform from Aptimiz makes it possible to analyze working time. To do this, visualization tools present the analysis of working time from a technical, economic, and organizational point of view.</p>
How to Implement:	<ol style="list-style-type: none">① Install the Aptimiz application on a smartphone or obtain the AZ21 GPS sensor sold by Aptimiz.② Contact Aptimiz team for account configuration③ The application runs in the background on the phone. The breeder accesses his data through the web interface.
Expected Benefits:	Have a global and detailed vision of the distribution of work in order to be able to calculate the hourly profitability for the control of the time spent on each work. The collection is automated, which limits data entry.

Country:

France

Production System (dairy or/and meat sheep/goat):

All

Category of Animal (ewe, goat, replacement, lamb, kid):

All

Source of Information:<https://techcare-project.eu/>

Prerequisites and/or limits

To use this management software, you must have a smartphone always with you and fully charged with Aptimiz application or the AZ221 GPS sensor sold by Aptimiz (it replaces the smartphone by offering the same functionalities as the application with a battery life of several days of charging). This is an offline operation, and no network is needed. The entire working group involved in the farm (partners, employees) must be equipped with this tool. These automatic recordings must be accompanied by discussion times, to optimize this tool.

Costs and Challenges

- Subscription required: Yes, annual ~ 200- 500 €
- Ease of use? Scale 1 (Complicated) – 10 (Simple)

- Value for money (for this type of benchmark farm)? Yes
- Recommend this tool/technology for use on other types of farm? Yes

This tech works for me because I can improve my travel times and analyse the time-consuming tasks on my farm and see if I can improve my time distribution. It also could be a new data based for the discussions with my advisor.

FARMER FROM FRANCE

It would take xx years for xx% adoption in xxx.

www.smartplatform.network

Dairy parlour EID reader

Need: Single identification of animals on milking parlour entrance

Aim: Collecting individual milk production animal data

Description:

- Sheep are identified by their ruminal bolus or ear-tag.
- When the animal pass through the tunnel the antenna reads its transponder.
- Once identified, each animal is placed in its respective position according to the order of entry.
- In this way milk yields will be associated with each individual animal.

How to Implement:

- You need to have all your animals tagged.
- Only when the milking machine is switched on, the RFID reading can be taken.
- DelPro PC Program extracts data of individual animal.

Country:

Italy

Production System (dairy or/and meat sheep/goat):

Dairy sheep and goat

Category of Animal (ewe, goat, replacement, lamb, kid):

Ewes and goats

Source of Information:

<https://techcare-project.eu/>

Attachment/links:

I think this is a very useful technology that still requires a lot of skills for its use
FARMER FROM ITALY

Expected Benefits:

- The system enables to identify animals and register their individual milk yield, being able to intervene on production drops.

Costs and Challenges

- All animals need an RFID tag. A PC management program is needed to couple electronic identification with milk production.

- Set up costs ~ > 10,000 Euro
- Subscription required: No
- Ease of use? Scale 1 (Complicated) – 10 (Simple)

- Value for money (for this type of benchmark farm)? Yes
- Recommend this tool/technology for use on other types of farm? Yes

It would take 16 years for 29 % adoption in dairy sheep.

It would take 14 years for 98 % adoption in dairy sheep.

Automatic feeders

Need: Concentrate distribution at milking or in the box

Aim: Collecting individual feed intake animal data

Description:

- Sheep are identified using their ear tags.
- If the animal is allowed access to a specific manger the gate goes down. When the allowed access time for that period is over, the access gate goes up, pushing the animal away from the manger so that another animal can get to the gate.
- The weight of the manger is measured before and after animal access and the weight difference is transferred to the central computer for analysis.

How to Implement:

- You need to have all your animals tagged.
- The manger is placed on a frame and rests on two electronic load cells. By turning the manger, it is easy to empty and clean it.
- BioControl's PC Program extracts data of individual animal.

Country:

Italy

Production System (dairy or/and meat sheep/goat):

Dairy sheep and goat

Category of Animal (ewe, goat, replacement, lamb, kid):

Ewes and goats

Source of Information:

<https://techcare-project.eu/>

Attachment/links:

<https://youtu.be/FNC1csOd6p4>

I think this is a very useful technology that still requires a lot of skills for its use

FARMER FROM ITALY

Expected Benefits:

- The system enables to feed animals according to their individual requirements even if they share the same pen.
 - To feed different rations to different animals in the same group. The system will automatically close the gate when the animal has reached the expected intake of its ration
-

Costs and Challenges

- All animals need an EID tag and a PC management program is needed
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- Set up costs ~ > 15,000 Euro
- Subscription required: No
- Ease of use? Scale 1 (Complicated) – 10 (Simple)

- Value for money (for this type of benchmark farm)? Yes
- Recommend this tool/technology for use on other types of farm? Maybe

It would take 5 years for 17 % adoption.

Automatic grass plate meter

Need:

- Timely weaning
- Outdoor condition / barn condition to monitor / adapt

Aim:

- To measure and manage grassland grazing

Description: Automatic plate measure that measures and records compressed sward height, to help inform grazing management decisions. The information collected allows the average amount of grass available in kilograms of dry matter per hectare (kg DM/ha) to be calculated.

Data can often be transferred to mobile devices and farm software packages. Depending on the type of measure used, they may also be used with GPS technology, linked to farm maps, to identify individual paddocks/fields.

How to Implement: Once the plate meter has been set-up and linked to an associated app (if applicable), the device should be ready to start measuring. Once in the field, move a few metres away from any fences/gateways and place the plate on top of the pasture, with as little pressure as possible. Start walking across the field taking regular measurements as you go.

A common and recommended method is to walk the field in a W shape, collecting 30 – 40 measurements per field. However, more measurements may be required if there is a lot of variation within the field.

Once you have taken the number of measurements you want, the device will provide you with an average kg DM/ha value. The data can then be transferred to a software package of your choice, to allow informed decisions to be made as to how best to use the grass available. The information can be used to calculate the total available grass in the paddock/field, total growth since the last measurement was taken and average daily growth etc.

FKO

Country:

UK

Production System (dairy or/and meat sheep/goat):

All

Category of Animal (ewe, goat, replacement, lamb, kid):

All

Source of Information:

Attachment/Links:

Farmers Weekly Video– How to use a plate meter:

[How to use a plate meter \(youtube.com\)](https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=aBUzLeTINA)

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=aBUzLeTINA>

Slide 1

FK0

Expected benefits to include relevant information from CBA

Fiona Kenyon, 2024-05-27T09:11:32.350

Expected Benefits:

- Once set-up, easy to collect measurements.
- Monitoring grass growth
- Allocating grazing resources to different groups of animals
- Useful for rotational grazing systems
- Utilising grass efficiently
- Feed budgeting
- Reseeding decisions

Costs and Challenges

- Set up costs ~ 501 – 1,000 Euro
- Subscription required: No
- Regularly collected measurements increase accuracy and benefits.
- If there is a lot of variation within the field, more measurements may be required.
- Make sure grass doesn't become stuck in the sensor below the plate.
- Mainly useful for improved and/or semi-improved grazing. Might not be so practical for extensive hill ground grazing.
- Ease of use? Scale 1 (Complicated) – 10 (Simple)

- Value for money (for this type of benchmark farm)? Yes
- Recommend this tool/technology for use on other types of farm? Yes

This tech works for me because it allows me to allocate my fields to different animals, based on their requirements and the availability of grass.

FARMER FROM UNITED KINGDOM

It would take 11 years for a peak adoption rate of 90%.

Sm@ll Ruminant Technologies

Automatic milk feeder

Need:

There is a need in a dairy goat and dairy sheep farm to wean lambs earlier so that their mothers can be milked for milk production.

Even in larger meat sheep farms, it may be necessary to use milk feeder to feed the lambs with milk replacer if their mothers have low milk yield or they have too many lambs or they reject their lambs.

Aim:

To ensure easily accessible *ad lib* feeding of weaned goat kids/lambs with milk replacer.

Offer the lambs freshly mixed milk made from a milk replacer at an desired temperature

Description:

- Milk feeder that mixes and refills automatically goat/sheep milk powder and water
- Warms and maintains milk at the desired temperature (30-40 °C) that can be determined regulated by the farmer
- Eight pipes lead from this unit to eight teats that the kids can suckle *ad lib* 24 hours a day up the 2 months of age or longer

How to Implement:

The goat kids are removed from their dams on the second day of life. From that time until the age of around two months the kids/lambs are kept in two age groups (4 + 4 teats) and offered milk replacer's milk *ad lib* from the teats. They are also offered clean hay, concentrates and clean water. The kids may need some training to use the teats, but normally they learn soon. The kids should also be observed to check that they are feeding, alongside regular observation for their well being

This tech works for me because it reducing labour costs and time for rearing kids

FARMER FROM ESTONIA

Country:

Estonia

Production System (dairy or/and meat sheep/goat):

Dairy sheep and goat (also possible in meat sheep indoor farms)

Category of Animal (ewe, goat, replacement, lamb, kid):

Kids, lambs

Source of Information:

Attachment/links:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ve5gvDqdbuo>

Expected Benefits:

Consistent quality of milk replacer offered and the means of access.

Higher intakes of the kids, less scouring, less disease and mortality.

Reduced aggression.

Reduced labour costs and time.

Costs and Challenges

Availability of necessary space and suitability of housing to fit requirements.

The kids may show preference for one teat, and queue up to use this preferred teat rather than suckling on the other teats.

The device needs maintenance twice a week.

Availability of water and electricity supply

- Set up costs ~ 3500 Euro
- Subscription required: No
- Ease of use? Scale 1 (Complicated) – 10 (Simple)

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

- Value for money (for this type of benchmark farm)? Yes
- Recommend this tool/technology for use on other types of farm? Yes

Link:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ve5gvDqdbuo>

It would take xx years for xx adoption.

www.smartplatform.network

Sm@ll Ruminant Technologies

Camera

Need:	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Have more time for lambing• Identification of ewes for lambing• Observation of changing behaviour
Aim:	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Monitoring of estrus, births, and injuries• Violations and general monitoring of the farm• Visualization of the strategic locations of the barn• Monitoring of automated systems
Description:	<p>The viewing is in real-time, and the control can be on laptop, tablet, smartphone.</p> <p>There is a motion detection and on-demand recording, and it is possible to have infrared night vision and soundtrack.</p> <p>The coverage area can be more than 50m² depending on the model.</p> <p>Cameras are resistant to the agricultural environment, they are waterproof and dustproof.</p>
How to Implement:	<p>Cameras are better suited to small lots because of their range. It's important to gauge the range according to the size of the lot, the height of the building and the brightness for best visibility.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Equipment: internet connection and smartphone or laptop for viewing• Storage: no humidity in the barn to avoid the formation of condensation
Expected Benefits:	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Safety: for the barn and the animals, less accidents, or infractions in the barn• Comfort: improved working conditions and less stress for the farmer• Time saving: remote viewing and recording

Country:

France

Production System (dairy or/and meat sheep/goat):

All

Category of Animal (ewe, goat, replacement, lamb, kid):

All

Source of Information:

https://idele.fr/?eID=cmis_download&oID=workspace://SpacesStore/b224f581-d145-4504-b354-cefb87b95a08

Prerequisites and/or limits :

- Depends on barn configuration and height
- Necessary communication network
- Image quality, zoom depending on the lens
- No night vision if no infrared cameras

Costs and Challenges

- Set up costs: 1 000 € - 2 500 €
- Subscription required: Yes / No depends on the use and device
- Ease of use? Scale 1 (Complicated) – 10 (Simple)

- Value for money (for this type of benchmark farm)? Maybe
- Recommend this tool/technology for use on other types of farm? Yes

This tech works for me because I can check if all this animals are ok in the shed. It also limits my travel time during the beginning or the end of lambing, because I can check if there is a problem or an imminent lambing.

FARMER FROM FRANCE

It would take between 6 and 11 years for 12% to 98% adoption in Hungary, Ireland, Italy and Norway.

www.smartplatform.network

Sm@ll Ruminant Technologies

Connected fences

Need: Time saving for fence monitoring,

Aim: Simplify the organization of work and improve safety with real-time diagnosis of the status of the installation of electric fences,

Description: In case of malfunction (power failure of the electrical substation, interruption of the fence, drop in voltage, weak substation battery, earth fault, etc.) and therefore of the risk of the animals escaping, the breeder receives an alert on his mobile phone via SMS and on his email.

The device communicates via the Sigfox Internet of Things network to the Vigifence servers. The use of Sigfox technology is justified by its very good coverage of the territory with more than 94% efficiency.

When a power failure is detected, the battery is low or the device itself is broken, the service automatically sends a sms alert on the breeder's phone. The user receives a proof of life every day to assure him of the proper functioning of the device.

- Up to 2 years of battery life
- Low space requirement
- From -40 to +80°C
- 250g
- Waterproof case
- Sigfox network

How to Implement: Step 1 : Registration of the device box on the website

Step 2 : the user inserts the battery and connects the wires to the fence and to the ground, as for a tester

Data transmission via Sigfox is then effective. In case of malfunction of the fence, alert sms will be sent.

Expected Benefits:

- Real-time monitoring of the operating status of electric fences.

Country:

Production System (dairy or/and meat sheep/goat):

All

Category of Animal (ewe, goat, replacement, lamb, kid):

All

Source of Information:

<https://www.thingonair.com/boutique/produits/22-vigifence-pack.html>

Prerequisites and/or limits :

- To equip an area, the user buys the box for €207,50 excl VAT and chooses his alert service package depending on his use, 6 month (€35 excl VAT) or 12 months (€50 excl. VAT). There is also an all-inclusive pack, including a 2-year packages (€290 excl VAT).
- Although the tool is efficient for incident detection, it lacks a GPS system that would allow the malfunction point to be located remotely.

- Set up costs: 500 € - 1 000 €
- Subscription required: Yes, monthly ~ 1 € - 50 €
- Ease of use? Scale 1 (Complicated) – 10 (Simple)

- Value for money (for this type of benchmark farm)? Yes
- Recommend this tool/technology for use on other types of farm? Yes

This technology works for me because I can check remotely whether my fences are working properly, and if there's a problem, I get a text message on my phone.

FARMER FROM FRANCE

It would take 12 years for 16% adoption in Ireland.

www.smartplatform.network

Connected water meter

Need: Need references on ewes water consumption.

Aim:

- Measure water consumption at the water trough, batch or animal
- Detect a water leak
- Detect a problem in the lot

Description: A connected water meter makes possible to measure the volume of water consumed on all part of a barn (e.g. drinking trough) thanks to a pulse transmitter positioned on the meter.

The pulses emitted are proportional to the flow of water passing through this meter. The pulses can be recorded by a logger which stores and transmits this data to a gateway for live access on a website or smartphone application.

How to Implement: The water meter is placed on the pipe of the water trough to measure the water consumed by the ewes or lambs access to this water trough. An identification system can be placed near the drinking trough to know the frequentation of the drinking trough per animal. To have an accurate idea of the lot's consumption, all water trough must be equipped with a water meter. To know the consumption of an animal, it is important to be able to link the identification of the animal to the values measured by the water meter.

Expected Benefits:

- Knowledge of animal water consumption
- Alerts in case of problems on the water network
- Animal health and welfare alerts

Country:

Production System (dairy or/and meat sheep/goat):

All

Category of Animal (ewe, goat, replacement, lamb, kid):

All

Source of Information:

<https://techcare-project.Eu/>

Costs and Challenges

- A water meter per water trough, a pulse transmitter, a data recording and transmission system
- Link between the water meters and the identification of the animals to have the individual consumption
- Several animals are often present at the same time around the water trough

-
- Set up costs ~ 2000 € / 200 € if you already have a box
 - Subscription required: Yes, annual ~ 200- 500 €
 - Ease of use? Scale 1 (Complicated) – 10 (Simple)

- Value for money (for this type of benchmark farm)? Yes
- Recommend this tool/technology for use on other types of farm? Yes

This tech works for me because I can check which animal is going to the water trough and also know when there is a leak.

FARMER FROM FRANCE

It would take 22 years for 72% adoption in Estonia.

www.smartplatform.network

Sheep Handling Conveyor

Need:

- Detection common parasites/manage external parasites/and treatment
- Dosing/vaccinating sheep

Aim:

Restrain sheep while enabling the operator to administer vaccines, drenches etc. with minimal physical strain

Description:

The sheep conveyor moves and restrains sheep along a race at a speed pre-determined by the operator. The sheep are held upright and cannot move forward or backward in the conveyor. This allows the farmer to stay in one position on either side of the conveyor and administer treatments without moving. The conveyor speed can be adjusted and the sheep can be moved forward, held in one position, reversed or held on their back as required.

How to Implement:

The sheep need to be loaded/walked onto the conveyor as it is moving, some sheep will walk on themselves but others may need to be physically pushed forward. The farmer can pre-determine and adjust the speed of the conveyor, and position themselves as the sheep to move towards them.

Country:

Ireland

Production System (dairy or/and meat sheep/goat):

All systems

Category of Animal (ewe, goat, replacement, lamb, kid):

Ewes, replacements, rams and lambs

Attachment/links:

<https://smartplatform.network/sheep-conveyor/>

This tech works well when I need to dose or vaccinate large groups of ewes/lambs. It is also less physical strain than catching and holding ewes/lambs.

Irish farmer

Expected Benefits:

- Time saving
- Reduced physical strain on farmer
- Can complete multiple treatments at once

Costs and Challenges

- Some sheep may need to be pushed onto the conveyor
- Not suitable for heavily pregnant ewes
- Unable to carry out body condition scoring while animals are in the conveyor
- Large initial investment, thus requiring a large flock size to justify the cost.
- Can be difficult to get animals into the conveyor therefore requires an additional person working or effective sheepdog which defeats the purpose of labour saving.

- Set up costs ~ > 15,000 Euro, so large flock size is needed to justify investment
- Ease of use? Scale 1 (Complicated) – 10 (Simple)

- Value for money (for this type of benchmark farm)? No
- Recommend this tool/technology for use on other types of farm? Maybe

It would take 11 years for a peak adoption of 3%.

Ultra High Frequency RFID Ear Tag

Need:	Read tags of animals quickly and reliably
Aim:	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Electronic identification technology (RFID) based on Ultra high frequency radio waves• Very interesting properties for mass reading• Simultaneous multiple readings• Reading distance up to several meters• Recognition: individual and group
Description:	<p>The UHF (Ultra High Frequency) RFID (Radio Frequency IDentification) identification tag linked with a suitable antenna allows multiple and simultaneous readings of animals, at distances of several meters, unlike official tags (at low frequency). This device makes possible to read the identification numbers on lots of moving animals and adapts to individual proximity reading for the analysis of attendance at points of interest (watering trough, trough, for example).</p> <p>The UHF RFID electronic tag, positioned on the ear, is detected by the antenna connected to a fixed or portable reader that can be controlled on a smartphone. The reading distance adapts according to the adjustment of the power of the reader (few cm to 2.5m). The information is available on a server or can be read directly using a smartphone application.</p>
How to Implement:	<p>UHF RFID identification tags must be fitted on the entire herd when lambs or kids are born.</p> <p>The electronic tag must be placed on the left ear of the animal. The breeder must also be equipped with automatic readers compatible with these UHF RFID identification tag.</p>
Expected Benefits:	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Time saving: less targeted user gesture, possibility of adjusting the reading distance by modulating the power.• Traceability: functional and comparable to low frequency, reading distance slightly greater at low frequency• Interoperability: compatibility and links with many systems (milking robots, DAC, DAL, scales)

Country:

France

Production System (dairy or/and meat sheep/goat):

All

Category of Animal (ewe, goat, replacement, lamb, kid):

All

Source of Information:

<https://techcare-project.eu/>

Prerequisites
and/or limits :

- Possible loss of tags
- Impossible to read through an animal

Costs and
Challenges

- Set up costs: 5 000 € -15 000 € for the antenna and the box + 1 – 20 € per tag
- Subscription required: No
- Ease of use? Scale 1 (Complicated) – 10 (Simple)

- Value for money (for this type of benchmark farm)? Yes
- Recommend this tool/technology for use on other types of farm? Yes

This tech is tested in experimental farms to know what are the new uses to needs the UHF tags can have. The management of the health and welfare can be a way.

TECHNICIAN FROM FRANCE

Sm@ll Ruminant Technologies

DNA parentage

Need:	Difficult to manage flock with different mating groups
Aim:	To know the pedigree of each lamb without the need for artificial insemination (AI), single-sire mating groups and/or recording at lambing time.
Description:	A service that provides animal parentage information using DNA collected as a tissue sample. Particularly useful for flocks that mate ewes in multi-sire groups and/or that lamb outside (in fields or on extensive hill grazing).
How to Implement:	<p>When starting this process, all animals in the flock need to be sampled using a tissue sampler supplied by several different companies (either using a stand-alone sample tube or one that is connected to ear-tag). Each sample must be labelled with the animal's unique identification number.</p> <p>Each year after that, only new animals joining the flock need to be sampled, for example newly purchased rams or replacement females (if not home-bred) and all new lambs born. Once all samples have been collected, they are sent to a laboratory for analysis.</p> <p>Results provided can range from simply the sire and dam of each animal to information on specific genes, depending on which service provider is used.</p>

Country:

UK

Production System (dairy or/and meat sheep/goat):

Meat sheep

Category of Animal (ewe, goat, replacement, lamb, kid):

All

Source of Information:

Attachment/Links:

[Sm@RT Digifarm testimony - UK - DNA tissue collection \(youtube.com\)](#)

[Sm@RT UK Innovative Farmer testimony - Southfield farm \(DNA Parentage\) \(youtube.com\)](#)

Expected Benefits:

- Sire and Dam information for each lamb.
- Removes the need for artificial insemination (AI), single-sire mating groups and/or recording at lambing time.
- Allows farmers to assess ewe rearing performance (e.g. lamb growth and survival) and ram mating success rate (number of lambs sired).
- Allows extensively managed flocks to be part of genetic breeding programmes.
- Potential for additional information relating to specific genes or genomic breeding values.

Costs and Challenges:

- Costly to sample all animals initially.
- Correct tissue sampling devices must be used.
- All animals need to be individually identified (lambs need to be tagged when tissue sample is collected).

- Set up costs ~ 1 – 20 Euro (individual costs)
- Subscription required: No
- Ease of use? Scale 1 (Complicated) – 10 (Simple)

- Value for money (for this type of benchmark farm)? Yes
- Recommend this tool/technology for use on other types of farm? Yes

This tech works for me because it means I don't have to catch and tag lambs at birth, but I can still find out who the mother and father is.

FARMER FROM THE UNITED KINGDOM

It allows us to mate ewes using larger multi-sire mating groups, instead of having to use single-sire mating.

FARMER FROM THE UNITED KINGDOM

It would take 18 years for a peak adoption rate of 16%.

Sm@ll Ruminant Technologies

Drone

Need:

- Surveillance of animals on pasture and unfenced rangeland
- Surveillance of fence and other installations
- Moving of sheep, particularly in autumn / before winter and in rocky landscape to reduce health and safety risk
- Documentation

Aim:

- Save time and effort checking on animals in mountain rangelands and pastures
- Save time and effort when moving animals – for example gathering sheep in autumn
- Pictures taken by drone can be used for documentation
- Increase safety for people collecting animals in challenging terrain
- Inspect fences, buildings and other installations that are not easily accessible

Description:

Drones can be used to monitor animals on pasture – checking on their health and whereabouts. This enables the farmer to check stock, for example if ewe and lambs are together. The camera can zoom in from a distance to get detailed information, without stressing the animals. Thermal camera can be used, particularly in forest areas, to help detect sheep.

Drones can also be used to move sheep. The pilot can remain in a fixed position or choose a safe and easy path, using the drone to guide animals.

Autonomous drones for 'Search and Rescue-missions' is, as of now, not allowed.

How to Implement:

- Purchase a drone (in Norway it is common that farmers with sheep in the same rangelands collaborate.)
- In order to obtain a license to fly a drone, you need to complete a course on regulations (Norway).
- Learn how to operate the drone.
- Fly drone in rangeland areas and pastures, as required.
- With an open category license the drone must be flown in Visual Line of Sight (VLOS)

Country:

Norway

Production System (dairy or/and meat sheep/goat):

Sheep and goat

Category of Animal :

ewe, goat, replacement, lamb, kid

Source of Information:

Personal communication with Norwegian farmers

Attachment/links:

[Sm@RT solutions Norway: Drone \(youtube.com\)](#)

Expected Benefits:

- Labour saving
- Knowledge of conditions in rangelands
- Detection of animals
- Less stress for farmer and animals
- Documentation

Costs and Challenges

- Cost: 800 – 7000 €
- Subscription required: No
- Ease of use? Scale 1 (Complicated) – 10 (Simple)

- Value for money (for this type of benchmark farm)? Yes
- Recommend this tool/technology for use on other types of farm? Yes
- Requires pilot training and a license: The open category licence (Norway) allows drone flying in 'Visual Line of Sight (VLOS)'.
• For drone pilot to fly Beyond Visual Line of Sight (BVLOS) there is a need for an advanced license and drone.
- Use of drone may be restricted by weather conditions (wind, rain).
- Battery capacity restricts flying time.

*The drone is very useful in the management of my farm.
It does not replace a good sheep dog or GPS-tracking of the ewes in the rangelands, but it is certainly a good supplement to those things.*

Sheep Farmer from Norway

It would take 13 years for 98% adoption in Norway.

www.smartplatform.network

Dynamic Milk Tank Weight

Need: Monitor and record lot and herd production at milking.

- Aim:**
- Automatically measure and record the weight of the tank at defined time intervals
 - Measure the milk production of the herd per milking
 - Measures the milk production of each lot per milking
 - Monitor the evolution of production during the campaign.
-

Description: The dynamic tank weighing device automatically measure and record the weight of the milk tank using weight sensors and a recording and transmission box. A display box also allows to read the weight of the tank in live. The data is accessible using dedicated software which allows time-stamped weight data files to be downloaded.

How to Implement: A weight sensor is installed under each leg of the tank. The different strain gauges are wired to a junction box then to a weight display box which requires a power supply. And this is connected to a "box", powered by 220 V, which records weight data and transmits it via an internet connection. The user can then access to the recordings from specific software installed on his computer.

The tare function allows to record only the weight of the milk arriving in the tank. Recording can be set at the desired frequency. An option allows you to force a reading using a badge to record weights at specific times. For example, this can make it possible to record the weight of the tank before and after milking a batch of animals to know the production of this group of individuals. Knowing the number of animals being milked can then make it possible to calculate production averages per lot/for the herd and per milking.

Country:

Production System (dairy or/and meat sheep/goat):

Dairy sheep and goat

Category of Animal (ewe, goat, replacement, lamb, kid):

Lactating ewes and goats

Source of Information:

<https://techcare-project.eu/>

Attachment/links:

Expected Benefits:

- Automatic recording of production data per milking at the herd and lot level
- Knowledge of milk production levels
- Study of the evolution of production in connection with the feeding of lactating animals, with the environmental conditions in breeding buildings or even information on the health of the herd, etc.

Costs and Challenges

- One device per milk tank, one weight sensor per tank foot.
- Metal supports for strain gauges, resistant to the weight of the tank but also to washing water (acids, bases).
- An internet connection accessible
- Access to electrical outlets to power the boxes.
- A measurement at the scale of the herd or lot.
- Requires recording the number of animals per milking to enhance the data with production averages.
- Be careful not to damage the cables leaving the load cells.

- Set up costs ~ XXX Euro
- Subscription required: Yes/No
- Ease of use? Scale 1 (Complicated) – 10 (Simple)

- Value for money (for this type of benchmark farm)? Maybe
- Recommend this tool/technology for use on other types of farm? Yes

*This tech works for me because
xxxxxx xxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxx*

FARMER FROM FRANCE

It would take xx years for xx adoption.

www.smartplatform.network

EID-enabled weigh crate and autodrafter

Need:

- Deciding on feeding groups / links between the state of the animals & feeding
- Auto drafting ewes for nutrition management
- Recognising and/or weighing your sheep automatically
- Lamb weighing (in barn and also in pasture)
- Animal sorting, manipulations, moving
- Drafting fat lambs / lambs to keep
- Timely weaning

Aim:

To help and/or improve flock management, during a number of different tasks throughout the production year, using a weigh crate that can read the electronic identification (EID) ear tag/bolus of an animal.

Description:

A weigh crate that has EID reading capabilities which, when combined with an electronic weigh head, can identify each animal when it is weighed by its EID ear tag / bolus. These systems can be fixed in one position or included in mobile handling systems.

How to Implement:

Depending on the capabilities of the electronic weigh head used, weigh data and additional information can be recorded and stored on the weigh head. If the weigh crate is an auto-drafter, the weigh head can automatically draft animals into pre-determined groups. If the weigh crate is not an auto-drafter, the weigh head can advise which direction the animal should be drafted to (which the user then does manually).

Country:

UK

Production System (dairy or/and meat sheep/goat):

Meat sheep

Category of Animal (ewe, goat, replacement, lamb, kid):

All

Source of Information:

Attachment/Links:

[Sheep electronic identification at SRUC – youtube](#)

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=cwS4ii8nRLs>

How to Implement (cont'd):

Data can then be downloaded on to a computer. Ideally when setting up the weigh head, information relating to all animals in the flock is uploaded (for example their EID tag/bolus number, sex, breed, year of birth, management group etc.).

Before each weighing session, the user should decide what drafting criteria they wish to implement. Examples include criteria can be based on the weight of each animal (for example over a certain weight for identifying animals ready for slaughter); the pregnancy scanning result for each animal (splitting animals in to different feeding groups based on the number of foetus identified at scanning); the body condition score of the animal (for example splitting leaner animals into a separate group for preferential feeding) or by management group (for example identifying individual ewes to go in to certain mating groups).

Once the weigh head has all the information entered that the criteria set requires, it will either auto-draft the animal into the correct pen or it will indicate which pen the animal should go to.

Expected Benefits:

- Improved flock record keeping
- Data collected for each individual animal.
- Labour and time saving
- Reduced stress and handling
- Improved flock efficiency
- Improved health and welfare
- Useful for breeding programmes

Costs and Challenges:

- All animals must be EID tagged (~1.20 € each)
- Suitable handling facilities
- Power supply (main or battery)
- Purchase costs can vary considerably (from simple manual weigh crates and weigh heads to crates with auto-drafting capabilities and more complex weigh head capabilities – from 5,000 € to 15,000 €)
- Requires training to get the most from the system
- There is no technical support on farm after purchase

This tech works for me because it is fast to use and gathers a lot of data in a short amount of time.

FARMER FROM THE UNITED KINGDOM

It would take 16 years for 24% adoption.

www.smartplatform.network

Environmental station

Need: Shed environment (humidity, temperature) control is difficult

Aim: It controls the environmental condition of the shed

Description:

- It allows to check the microclimate of the farm and helps the animals to overcome unscathed the periods characterized by high temperature
- It allows to move uniformly a higher air flow rate
- The ventilation system can be managed in automatic mode to regulate the functioning of the entire system based on air temperature and humidity index (THI index) detected by appropriate probes.

How to Implement:

Air ventilation is set up to start when air humidity and temperature conditions overcome certain limits.

Country:

Italy

Production System (dairy or/and meat sheep/goat):

Dairy sheep and goat

Category of Animal (ewe, goat, replacement, lamb, kid):

Lactating ewes and goats

Source of Information:

<https://techcare-project.eu/>

Attachment/links:

https://youtu.be/lcK_w_uGANU

Expected Benefits:

- It improves the environmental condition of the barn
- The system enables to ameliorate animal welfare conditions and prevent heat stress.
- It prevents performance losses during lactation and reproduction phases

Costs and Challenges

- Humidity and temperature control unit system

- Set up costs ~ 5,001 – 15, 000 Euro
- Subscription required: No
- Ease of use? Scale 1 (Complicated) – 10 (Simple)

- Value for money (for this type of benchmark farm)? Yes
- Recommend this tool/technology for use on other types of farm? Yes

This technology proves to be very useful for supporting high milk production, especially during periods when temperatures increase significantly
FARMER FROM ITALY

Sm@ll Ruminant Technologies

FECPAK-G2

Need:

- Detection common parasites/manage internal parasites/and treatment
- Parasitism detection/faecal egg sampling/when to treat/how well wormer treatments have worked

Aim:

Undertake faecal egg counts using an internet connected, image based diagnostic platform which can be done without a laboratory.

Description:

FECPAK G2 kit is a diagnostic platform which allows one to undertake faecal egg counts without the requirement for a laboratory or the need to send faecal samples to a laboratory. It is image based which allows sampling to be undertaken at any time and uploaded through the computer software. Results are returned to the person who uploads the sample images within 24 hours.

How to Implement:

Fresh faecal samples need to be collected

Detailed instructions and videos are provided which show how to prepare the faecal sample.

Results are returned to the person who uploads the sample images within 24 hours

Country:

UK

Production System (dairy or/and meat sheep/goat):

Dairy and meat sheep

Category of Animal (ewe, goat, replacement, lamb, kid):

Sheep and goats, all ages

Source of Information:

Attachment/Links:

[FECPAKG2 technology for easy and accurate Faecal Egg Count testing. \(youtube.com\)](#)

How to Implement (cont'd):

The device requires internet connection to upload the image to the FECPAK software (<https://online.fecpakg2.com/login>)

Expected Benefits:

- Can help to optimize worm control and check how well treatments have worked.
- Can be undertaken by anyone without laboratory facilities
- Fast results

Costs and Challenges:

- Requires internet access
 - Uses a different protocol and set of equipment to diagnose liver fluke infection
 - Monthly subscription required
 - Ease of use? Scale 1 (Complicated) – 10 (Simple)
- 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10
- Value for money (for this type of benchmark farm)? Maybe
 - Recommend this tool/technology for use on other types of farm? Yes

It would take 8 years for 58% adoption in the UK.

Feed Ration Planner

Need:

- Grazing monitoring & Feed transition from grazing to housing
-

Aim:

- Assessing the grazing and feed requirements of animals at different points throughout the year.
-

Description:

AHDB – Feed (grass and supplementation) budget planner: Helps farmers forecast how much grass is going to be available at certain times of the year and helps to plan when supplementation may be required.

How to Implement:

The planner is free to download from the AHDB website. Once downloaded, begin by filling in the initial pasture cover value (in kg DM/ha) based on compressed sward heights. Then fill in the details associated with the grazing area (ha), number of grazing days each month, rate of grass growth (kg DM/ha/day) and the predicted utilisation of grass (%). Using the information provided, the planner calculates the difference between grass growth and animal intake requirements.

There is then an option to add additional data regarding the use of any supplement feeds (hay, silage & concentrates) each month. Different types of animals can be allocated to the pastures (Ewes, Lambs (once they are weaned) and Growing Cattle). The planner provides graphs showing pasture cover throughout the year and the relationship between supply and demand throughout the year, based on the information provided.

There is also a planner for those using rotational grazing and additional information as to the intake requirements of the different animals (and their stages) provided.

Country:

UK

**Production System
(dairy or/and meat
sheep/goat):**

Meat and dairy sheep
and goats

**Category of Animal
(ewe, goat,
replacement, lamb,
kid):**

All

**Source of
Information:**

Attachment/links:

Feed budget planner

[How to use the full feed budget planner - YouTube](#)

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=gUjUw9q3Xu4>

**Rotational grazing
planner**

[How to use a rotation planner - YouTube](#)

https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=1adt_lp6vno

Expected Benefits:

- Allows farmers to plan how they are going to manage and utilise their grazing (and supplementary feed stocks) based on the demands of their animals throughout the year.
- Better grass utilisation.
- The intake requirements of the animals can be better met.

Costs and Challenges

- Set up costs ~ Nothing (Free)
- Subscription required: No
- The tool is free but requires regular measurements using a plate meter/sward stick to collect pasture data.
- Mainly useful for improved and/or semi-improved grazing. Might not be so practical for extensive hill ground grazing.
- Data collected can be used with some mobile phone apps and farm management software (some of these may involve a subscription fee).
- More sophisticated ration software are available, which come at a cost, but allow more detailed rations to be set-up for various different classes of animal (pregnant ewes, finishing lambs, etc.).
- e.g. **DietCheck for Sheep** - <https://dietcheck.co.uk/software/dietcheck-for-sheep>.
- **Small Ruminant Nutrition System** - ([Model: SRNS \(nutritionmodels.com\)](http://Model:SRNS(nutritionmodels.com)))

- Ease of use? Scale 1 (Complicated) – 10 (Simple)

- Value for money (for this type of benchmark farm)? Yes
- Recommend this tool/technology for use on other types of farm? Yes

It would take 11 years for a peak adoption rate of 86%.

Flock Management Software

Need:

There is a need to analyze data from sheep and goat farms, but usually, no data is available.

Flocks are getting bigger and if we want to record data on farm - birth, pregnancy, vaccinations, diseases, etc. we need to be able to collect data and then analyze it.

Aim:

Collect data from many on farm devices - parlor, milk tank, pedometers, weighting devices, etc. to create a reliable output

Description:

This software can be installed on the farm PC, on the farmer's smartphone, or on any device with an internet connection.

How to Implement:

From the installation of the software and the registration data is collected.

Some devices can upload the data automatically and some data may require manual input.

The software is capable of showing all relevant analysis to breeders, consultants, veterinarians, and so on.

The software works on three levels:

- Individual animal
- Group
- Whole farm

Country:

Israel

Production System (dairy or/and meat sheep/goat):

Dairy sheep and goat

Category of Animal (ewe, goat, replacement, lamb, kid):

Ewe, goat

Source of Information:

Attachment/links:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=4qdeQRjyKy4>

It's hard today to understand how we managed before

ARIE BE'ER
FARMER

Expected Benefits:

- Consistent knowing of the farm situation on all levels- animal, group, and flock.
- All the data, analysis, and advice are in one place, all very accessible.
- There is data from the past, and data from the present, so it's possible to get a forecast for the future.

Costs and Challenges

The software installation and registration.

- Set up costs ~ free
- Subscription required: yes
- Cost is 50-100 Euro monthly per flock, depending on flock size.

• Ease of use? Scale 1 (Complicated) – 10 (Simple)

- Value for money (for this type of benchmark farm)? Yes
- Recommend this tool/technology for use on other types of farm? Yes

Sheep ID	Sex	Number of Lambs	Fertility	Age at Birth	Average for Lifetime use	Days Between Lambings	Mortality
1	♀	111	0	1.71	0	104.75	0
2	♀	7	1.0	0	0.00	104.07	1
3	♀	230	0.0	0.00	0.00	104.71	0
4	♀	100	0.0	0.00	0.00	103.00	0
5	♀	100	0.0	0.00	0.00	101	1
6	♀	14	0.0	0.00	0.00	104.00	0
7	♀	230	0.0	0.00	0.00	104.00	0
8	♀	0	0.0	0.00	0.00	104.00	0
9	♀	0	0.0	0.00	0.00	100	0
10	♀	230	0.0	0.00	0.00	104	0
11	♀	0	0.0	0.00	0.00	103.0	0
12	♀	0	0.0	0.00	0.00	100	0
13	♀	0	0.0	0.00	0.00	100.0	1

It would take 14 years for 98% adoption in the UK.

www.smartplatform.network

Sm@ll Ruminant Technologies

Flock Recording App

Need:

- Recording/collecting/analysing health data is time-consuming/recording tags health issues, including withdrawal period
- Combining of individual health data and all other data
- Lambing records/ewe performance
- Performance recording (growth rates, slaughter data etc.)
- Added value of digital technologies (cost, use of technologies at some periods)

Aim:

Recording individual animal production/performance

Description:

Flock recording apps (e.g. Sheep Ireland) can be used to performance record individual animals in a flock. Depending on the app, data recorded such as weights, mating information, litter size, parentage, medicine use etc. This facilitates the comparison of animal performance within and between flocks. Data can be input manually or the app can be linked to an EID reader through Bluetooth and record animal EID/tag number automatically. The app will store this information and reports can be generated depending on data recorded e.g. growth rates.

How to Implement:

All animals need to be individually identified i.e. tagged. Open the app on your smartphone, input the animal ID or scan their tag with an EID reader and record data as required. The data is then uploaded and saved online when the phone is connected to the internet.

Country:

IRELAND

Production System (dairy or/and meat sheep/goat):

Dairy and meat sheep

Category of Animal (ewe, goat, replacement, lamb, kid):

Ewes

Attachment/Links:

<https://smartplatform.network/flock-recording-app-sheep-ireland/>

Expected Benefits:

- Saves time
- Helps selecting replacements/culls
- Collates flock data
- Provides ancestral information to facilitate mating groups

Costs and Challenges:

- Need to have smartphone that can download the app
- Internet connection needed to upload information
- Set up costs ~ minimal if you already have a smartphone
- Subscription is free for commercial flocks and €50-100 for pedigree flocks
- Ease of use? Scale 1 (Complicated) – 10 (Simple)
- Value for money (for this type of benchmark farm)? Yes
- Recommend this tool/technology for use on other types of farm? Yes

This tech works for me because it provides ancestral information when I am selecting which rams to mate with my ewes. It helps to prevent inbreeding.

IRISH FARMER

It would take 16 years for peak adoption of 6%.

GPS collar/E-bell

Need:	Surveillance of animals on pastures, particularly in large rangeland areas.
Aim:	<p>Improved surveillance and animal welfare for grazing livestock</p> <p>Alarms when there is something wrong with an animal on pasture</p> <p>Timesaving and improved revenue for farmers</p> <p>Realtime data on whereabouts of livestock</p> <p>Ease of finding and gathering animals from rangeland pastures in the autumn</p>
Description:	<p>A GPS-collar / E-bell provide realtime information on the position of an animal. This information can be monitored from laptop, tablet or smartphone.</p> <p>In addition to providing the position of an animal the GPS-collar commonly also provide:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A geofence function: Define areas in the map and get alerts to your smartphone if the animal moves into or out of the area. • Alerts from position and activity sensors: If the sensor(s) detects unusual behaviour it will transmit an alert to the farmers smartphone. Alerts provided may be: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Low activity (i.e. animal is sick) or high activity (i.e. animal is chased). • No movement. • No change in position. • Mortality alert. • Analysis of grazing activity: I.e. heat maps of where animals graze the most.
How to Implement:	<p>Buy GPS-collars / E-bells directly from the company. Commonly you also need to buy battery and subscription per season or per year.</p> <p>Activate E-bells in user portal on computer and/or turn on the E-bell via an app that is provided.</p> <p>Hang the E-bells on the collar and animal.</p> <p>During the grazing season you track your animals on the app/tablet/PC.</p> <p>Alerts if animals experience abnormal activity are provided.</p>

Country:

Norway

Production System (dairy or/and meat sheep/goat):

Meat sheep

Category of Animal (ewe, goat, replacement, lamb, kid):

Ewes

Source of Information:

Attachment/Links:

<http://www.telespor.no/>

<http://www.findmy.no/>

<http://www.gjetargut.no/>

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=YxcHJG1V5Vo>

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=yCGIxn u4t4Q&t=5s>

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=e7TlxmqTRo>

Expected Benefits:

- Efficient attention and overview of animals while grazing.
- Comfort: It gives the farmer more freedom and provides security for grazing animals.
- Time saving: The farmer saves time on both supervision of animals during grazing season and when gathering animals in the autumn.

Costs and Challenges:

- Availability of mobile network must be identified in order to choose the appropriate GPS collar provider. If mobile network is not available, a collar that communicates via satellite can be used.
- Wireless technologies like LTE-M, NB-IoT and LoRaWAN may be provided.
- Number of positions per day is limited due to battery capacity. Commonly a position report every 4th hour for 4 months can be expected.
- A two-way communication system is available for some GPS-collars, allowing adjustments of alarms and reports during grazing season. This is not provided by all.

- Individual costs ~ 50 – 200 Euro
- Subscription required: Yes

- Ease of use? Scale 1 (Complicated) – 10 (Simple)

- Value for money (for this type of benchmark farm)? Yes
- Recommend this tool/technology for use on other types of farm? Yes

We use it to have efficient attention to animals on summer mountain rangeland grazing. Particularly in autumn to locate animals in the mountains and gather them efficiently. Also, for breeding purposes i.e. to cull animals that graze in areas we do not want them to be.

Improvement suggestions: Improved battery capacity for more frequent reports. Alarms if odd behaviour. Better collaboration possibilities between farmers/users of tracking devices.

FARMER FROM NORWAY

It would take 7,5 years for 92 % adoption.

www.smartplatform.network

Sm@ll Ruminant Technologies

EID Hand Held Reader

Need:

- Recording/collecting/analysing health data is time-consuming. E.g. recording tags, health issues, tracking withdrawal periods
- Combining of individual health data and all other data
- Lambing records/ewe performance
- Identification of ewes/lambs
- Monitoring reproduction - identify ewes for insemination/tupping dates/ram health monitoring/fertility testing
- Recognising and/or weighing your sheep automatically
- Performance recording (growth rates, slaughter data etc.)
- Added value of digital technologies (cost, use of technologies all other data periods)

Aim:

To identify animals automatically, record data To identify animals automatically, record data and upload to database upload to database.

Description:

EID handheld reader/wand can be used to scan any animal which has an EID tag. Once identified, the device can be used to input data e.g. weight, body condition score. Readers can wirelessly connect with your weigh scale indicator using Bluetooth technology. Depending on the wand/reader more information can be input e.g. medical treatment, litter size, breeding information, lambing difficulty etc. Basic wands will only scan and record EID tags and session number, but more advanced readers are customisable for recording multiple types of data. The data is uploaded to a software package i.e. data base which can be viewed, compiled and reports generated.

How to Implement:

The wand/reader must be positioned near the animal's EID tag to identify the animals. Data can then be recorded, saved and uploaded to the software package.

Country:

Ireland

Production System (dairy or/and meat sheep/goat):

Dairy and meat sheep

Category of Animal (ewe, goat, replacement, lamb, kid):

Ewe, replacement, lamb

Source of Information:

<https://smartplatform.network/eid-handheld-reader/>

Attachment/links:

https://youtu.be/36-M-3sHXOA?si=iGYyW8fdwLZb_A3

Expected Benefits:

- Performance and health recording
- Parentage and litter size recording
- Facilitates selecting replacements
- Can record animal movement on/off farm

Costs and Challenges:

- Compatibility with other devices.
- Ease of data transfer to other software.
- Easy to use once installed.
- Easy to use.
- It is permanent investment, the lifetime of the technology is more than 5 years
- Reduced stress to the animals.
- Improved welfare of the animals.

- Set up costs ~ 1000-2500 Euro
- Subscription required: Yes/No (depends on software used)
- Ease of use? Scale 1 (Complicated) – 10 (Simple)

- Value for money (for this type of benchmark farm)? Yes
- Recommend this tool/technology for use on other types of farm? Yes

This tech works for me because it makes our work a lot easier

FARMER FROM HUNGARY

It would take 9 years for 77% adoption.

www.smartplatform.network

Electronic Milk Meter

Need:

There is a need in dairy goat and dairy sheep farming to measure milk yield at individual level.

Aim:

Collecting individual animal milk production automatically (every day) and managing animal's data

Description:

- It displays easy-to-read individual data on milk yield, instant milk flow and milking time duration in clear red digits (e.g. DeLaval) to simplify effective, daily flock management
- Milk conductivity and temperature may be recorded (e.g., AfiMilk, Lactocorder)

How to Implement:

- The flow milk meter must be positioned in the milking parlour
- All animals must be tagged and have their individual information entered into a software (DeLaval, AfiMilk or others)
- You need to have water and electricity availability
- You need to have a flock management software in order to collect and manage milk yield and animal data
- You need to calibrate the flow meters at least three time per year

This tech works for me because it allows me to select high producing animals from the flock

FARMER FROM ITALY

Country:

Italy

Production System (dairy sheep/goat)

Dairy sheep and goat

Category of Animal (ewe, goat):

Ewe, goats

Source of Information:

Attachment/links:

- <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=TeDvU nn3ViY>
- <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=gL1IYZ kVsQw&t=8s>

Expected Benefits:

- Milk yield and milking order individually monitored at each milking.
- Individual warnings based on milk yield drops and /or conductivity raising for an early detection of mastitis and other pathologies/distress conditions.
- Adequate feeding plans according to requirements.

Costs and Challenges

- Milk meters are quite expensive and require some maintenance. Training is necessary to learn how to use the technology and how to collect and manage data.
- Some models can be implemented to measure conductivity.
- Milking order can be related to mastitis or lameness issues.

- Set up costs ~ 5000 Euro/cluster
- Subscription required: No
- Ease of use? Scale 1 (Complicated) – 10 (Simple)

- Value for money (for this type of benchmark farm)?
Maybe
- Recommend this tool/technology for use on other types of farm? Maybe

★★★☆☆ It would take 16 years for 29% of adoption level in sheep.

★★★★☆ It would take 14 years for 98% of adoption level in goats.

Sm@ll Ruminant Technologies

Portable NIRS

Need: Evaluation of forage quality and comparison to references/chemical analysis of feedstuff on farm

Aim:

- Measuring on-farm the composition (moisture, starch, CP, NDF, ADF, Ash) of grain, conserved or fresh forages.

Description: It monitors the dry matter content of feed ingredients, improving the consistency of the rations. It checks the dry matter of forages in the field, helping to determine the right time for the harvest. It assesses the quality of the feed purchased and stocked.

How to Implement: You need to put the feed sample in to the cup analyser and read the results of the analysis in the display, print or store them in a USB key.

Country:

Italy

Production System (dairy or/and meat sheep/goat):

Dairy and meat sheep and goat

Category of Animal (ewe, goat, replacement, lamb, kid):

Ewes and goats

Source of Information:

<https://techcare-project.eu/>

Attachment/links:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=oaBde6DV-XY>

The portable NIR allows for a rapid assessment of feedstuff chemical composition. It would be desirable to include it in on-farm technical assistance services.

FARMER FROM ITALY

Expected Benefits:

- There is no sample preparation
- It is portable and can be moved easily by a trolley
- Less than one minute to read the results
- It allows to make real time decisions

Costs and Challenges

It needs:

1. a power supplier;
2. a software to be installed in a PC;
3. for some feedstuff (e.g. some fresh forages) may need a calibration based on wet chemistry.

- Set up costs ~ > 15, 000 Euro
- Subscription required: No
- Ease of use? Scale 1 (Complicated) – 10 (Simple)

- Value for money (for this type of benchmark farm)?
Maybe
- Recommend this tool/technology for use on other types of farm? Maybe

It would take 10 years for 98% of adoption.

Portable Somatic Cell Counter

Need: Early detection of troubles. Identification & separation of animals with problems

Aim:

- Monitoring mastitis and udder health management

Description:

- A portable somatic cell counter (i.e. DeLaval DCC) offers a rapid on-farm determination of somatic cell count.
- It allows you to detect mastitis at an early stage resulting in a cost effective control of mastitis and easier flock management.

How to Implement:

- The DCC is a portable instrument that gives results in just 45 seconds with simple to use disposable cassettes.
- Take a sample; Insert the cassette; Read the result (no. cells/ μ L of milk)

Country:

ITALY

Production System (dairy or/and meat sheep/goat):

Dairy sheep and goat

Category of Animal (ewe, goat, replacement, lamb, kid):

Lactating ewes and goats

Source of Information:

<https://techcare-project.eu/>

Attachment/links:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=C-Jf5mqMeOk>

The tool proved useful when doubts about the udder health of some animals appears.

FARMER FROM ITALY

Expected Benefits:

- Treatment of mastitis at an earlier stage
 - Quicker recovery and less production loss
 - More efficient control of the spread of mastitis
 - Less risk of penalties or loss of bonus payment
-

Costs and Challenges

- You need an DNA – specific fluorescent reagent
-

- Set up costs ~ 5000 Euro
- Subscription required: No

- Ease of use? Scale 1 (Complicated) – 10 (Simple)

- Value for money (for this type of benchmark farm)?
Maybe
- Recommend this tool/technology for use on other types of farm? Yes

It would take 9 years for 1% of adoption.

Sm@ll Ruminant Technologies

Hay drying technology for goats

Need:

Hay making traditionally depends on suitable weather. To get quality hay with high protein and energy content the grass should be at the right growth stage. However, quite often rain in this period makes it impossible to make hay at the correct growth stage. Additionally many dairy goat and sheep farmers prefer to feed their animals with hay diets (not silage) to reduce the exposure of Clostridial bacteria from silage into milk and to achieve high quality cheeses with a longer maturing time.

Aim:

To optimise the time of hay cutting at the ideal growth stage regardless of the weather conditions. To ensure consistent high quality grass-based forage for dairy goats throughout the year.

Description:

After the cut, the grass is allowed to wilt for one day (or less) on the field and is then transferred to bunkers. Drying system has various sensors for monitoring air temperature and humidity at different heights of the bunker during the post drying process. The system moves valves as needed. The system uses either warm dry air from attic room or switches on the dryer for removing excess moisture from the air. This is powered by electricity mainly sourced from solar panels. The barn has double ceiling under black tin roof. The sun heats black roof, the air is heated and directed through tunnels to the bunkers. The dried hay is delivered by a suspended forklift on overhead rails.

How to Implement:

The implementation of this technology is described in a section Description.

Country:

Estonia

Production System (dairy or/and meat sheep/goat):

Dairy goat, dairy sheep

Category of Animal (ewe, goat, replacement, lamb, kid):

Lactating, dry and young goats/ewes and bucks/rams. The whole flock.

Source of Information:

Attachment/Links:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=rWV-8ZAO8MU>

Expected Benefits:

Labour demands for the delivery and management of feed is reduced. The period of time taken for the whole process of hay-making is shortened, from cutting to storage, it can be completed in one/two days irrespective of the weather. As the post-cut hay spends little time lying on the ground (the drying process takes place indoors), there is less risk of contamination of the hay from soil and atmospheric microbes. In addition the nutritional quality parameters (including protein and energy) of the hay are higher and there is less need for concentrate feed. The consistent quality of the hay is expected to improve palatability and feed intakes. One person can manage the feeding and milking of 500 milking goats.

Costs and Challenges:

- Set up costs ~ > 15, 000 Euro
- Subscription required: No
- Availability of necessary space and suitability of housing to fit requirements. Availability and unpredictable costs of energy required to ventilate the drying bunkers and costs for bunkers.

- Ease of use? Scale 1 (Complicated) – 10 (Simple)

Maybe

- Recommend this tool/technology for use on other types of farm? Yes

This tech works for me because it allows to make a quality hay fast and in expected time

FARMER FROM ESTONIA

It would take xx years for xx adoption.

www.smartplatform.network

Pregnancy Scanner

Need:

- Scanning and grouping ewes for managing appropriate nutrition
- Distribution/management of concentrate allocation during lambing
- Lambing records/ewe performance
- Deciding on feeding groups/Link between the state of the animals & feeding

Aim:

- Determine ewe pregnancy and litter size, to facilitate nutrition management

Description:

Ewes can be scanned to diagnose pregnancy and expected litter size. This facilitates nutrition management pre-lambing. Expected lambing date can also be determined.

How to Implement:

A trained operator uses an ultrasound scanner and specially designed crate to quickly identify pregnancy and/or expected litter size. Ewes are marked to record litter size and barrenness, and EID recording may be used.

This tech benefits me because it requires no investment and isn't expensive. It saves money in concentrate costs too.

FARMER FROM IRELAND

This tech works for me because it allows me to identify and sell barren ewes before lambing and feed pregnant ewes according to their expected litter size.

FARMER FROM IRELAND

Country:

Ireland

Production System (dairy or/and meat sheep/goat):

Meat and dairy sheep and goats

Category of Animal (ewe, goat, replacement, lamb, kid):

Mature ewes, female goats and replacements

Source of Information:

<https://techcare-project.eu/>

Attachment/links:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ActZdYMIIfk>

Expected Benefits:

- Quick, stress free and undertaken with sheep in standing position in a designated crate.
- Identifies barren ewes that can be culled or sold.
- To facilitate nutrition management in late pregnancy. Ewes can be grouped according to expected litter size to avoid under or over nutrition.

Costs and Challenges

- Ewes should be restricted from feed for about 10 hours in advance of scanning
- Availability of trained operator with equipment
- Facilities to group and manage ewes according to expected litter size pre-lambing

- A contractor completes the scanning so no investment needed by the farmer.
- Can be used with performance recording application/software to develop data set of individual and flock performance.

- Ease of use? Scale 1 (Complicated) – 10 (Simple)

- Value for money (for this type of benchmark farm)?
Yes
- Recommend this tool/technology for use on other types of farm? Yes

It would take 3 years for a peak adoption rate of 97%.

Sm@ll Ruminant Technologies

Virtual fence

- Need:**
- Control where animals are allowed to stay and/or graze
 - Monitor animals on pastures and get notification of events: i.e. animals crossing boundaries and unnormal behaviour
 - Allocate new pasture without having to move physical fences

Aim: To control whereabouts of goats and sheep without putting up physical fences

Description: A virtual fence collar can control the whereabouts of animals. This can be needed for a number of reasons:

- Fence in animals without physical fence
- Fence animals out from an area
- Control whereabouts of animals
- Alerts on behaviour of animals
- Information about where animals graze/use of landscape
- Move to new pastures/edit existing pastures without physical fencing work

Animals must be provided a learning phase as described by the tech provider.

The boundaries of the pasture are set with a smart phone in the app belonging to the solution. The animal wears a collar with GPS and when the animal approaches the virtual boundary, it will first hear repeated sound signals (audio cues) before finally receiving an electric stimuli through the collar if it crosses the virtual fence line.

The animal owner gets a message in the app on animal behavior i.e. escaped animals and electric stimuli. The frequency of reports from collar can be adjusted in the app.

The boundary of the allocated pasture is a zone rather than a line. Precision depends on terrain (steep terrain gives less precision) and coverage by satellites at any given time.

The user can see in the app how much power is left in each collar. Some users report that their batteries last all summer, while others say they have to take their animals home to recharge their batteries. The collars also have a solar panel to charge battery.

Country:

Norway

Production System (dairy or/and meat sheep/goat):

All

Category of Animal (ewe, goat, replacement, lamb, kid):

Adult sheep and goats

Source of Information:

www.nofence.no

Personal communication with Norwegian farmers

Attachment/Links:

[Sm@RT solutions Norway - virtual fence \(youtube.com\)](https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=dlodXcn7M1A)

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=dlodXcn7M1A>

https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=jwOdiK_4eRs

How to Implement:

- Buy virtual fence collars for all adult animals.
- Download app on cellphone.
- Provide suitable learning facilities according to product guidelines.
- Assign in product app the recommended fence borders.

Expected Benefits:

- Saves time of putting up fences.
- Gives access to suitable and safe grazing areas, also where physical fencing would be challenging.
- Gives insight in animals' movements
- Gives alert when animals leave the authorised area, as well as if animals are moving less than normal

Costs and Challenges:

- +/- 200 € per collar plus subscription
- Subscription required: Yes, daily ~ 0,40 - 1 € per collar
- Need smartphone to receive alerts and location
- Need mobile coverage to get messages from system. However, the virtual fencing system on animal works without mobile coverage.
- Battery capacity depends on frequency of location reports, terrain and animal behaviour
- Precision of fence boundaries can vary
- GPS collars are only for adult animals, not for lambs

- Ease of use? Scale 1 (Complicated) – 10 (Simple)

- Value for money (for this type of benchmark farm)?
Non
- Recommend this tool/technology for use on other types of farm? Yes

The best thing about the virtual fence system is that I always know the whereabouts of my sheep. It's very interesting to see how they use the mountain pasture. I used to have a lot of stress with sheep leaving the grazing area at the other side of the mountain, but with the virtual fence system I'm in full control. I think I would have given up sheep farming without it.

SHEEP FARMER FROM NORWAY

This tech works for me because I can see the location of my animals and keep them in a chosen area without physical fences. The GPS is precise to find my goats in a scrub area.

FARMER FROM FRANCE

It would take 2-11 years for 61-98% adoption in Norway.

www.smartplatform.network

Walk over Weighing (WoW)

Need: Early detection of troubles (feeding, sanitary...),

Aim: Weight monitoring without additional work

Description: The Walk over Weighing is a weighing crate with less contention. It is composed of 2 weighing bars which ensure a dynamic weighing. This means that animals don't have to stop to be weighed, the scale calculates the means of several weight.

How to Implement: The scale must be positioned between two separate areas with a defined direction of travel through the scale (Example below).

Expected Benefits:

- Weight monitoring (At least one weight per week for each animal)
- Increase productivity (early detection of troubles)
- Gain of time (Less/No weighing session)

Country:

Production System (dairy or/and meat sheep/goat):

Dairy and meat sheep

Category of Animal (ewe, goat, replacement, lamb, kid):

Ewe

Source of Information:

<https://idele.fr/Otop-3D/>

Attachment/links :

<http://idele.fr/reseaux-et-partenariats/otop3d/publication/idelesolr/recommends/otop-3d-les-dispositifs-dacquisitions-sont-prets.html>

Prerequisites and/or limits:

- Have a flock management software
- Provide a learning time for animals
- Have “large”, accessible and flexible spaces

Costs and Challenges

- Set up costs: 5 000 € - 15 000 €
- Subscription required: No
- Ease of use? Scale 1 (Complicated) – 10 (Simple)

- Value for money (for this type of benchmark farm)? Yes
- Recommend this tool/technology for use on other types of farm? Yes

This tech works for me because I can follow the weight of my ewes which are in rangeland. With his solar panel the device works all the year, even under the snow !

FARMER FROM FRANCE

It would take 9 to 14 years for 31% to 63% adoption in France.

www.smartplatform.network

Sm@ll Ruminant Technologies

Weight recording water trough

Need: Introduce PLF based early warning system into sheep and goat production

- Aim:**
- Automatically collect individual animal weight and drinking habits data
 - Enable zero animal habituation to the new device/procedures
 - Zero interference with existing farmer processes and procedures
 - Optimize production
 - Increase animal welfare
-

Description:

The SmarTrough is fitted with multitude of sensors to record individual weight, water consumption and drinking habits of sheep/goats.

The collected data is processed by advanced algorithms to generate business insights to the farmer immediately.

The insights are then disseminated via a carefully crafted web interface to enable maximization of farm results.

How to Implement:

The SmarTrough is a plug and play product.

It is mounted, either on an existing trough or an integrated one.

Each SmartTrough may serve up to 120 animals

Multiple SmartTrough devices maybe be introduced seamlessly in the same yard, farm or pasture.

Once the device is in place, animals must use the sensor enriched troughs to drink, thus allowing the monitoring and capturing of weight and drinking habit data continuously.

The SmartTrough requires electricity, water supply and an internet connection to allow for data communication to server.

Country:

Israel

Production System (dairy or/and meat sheep/goat):

Dairy/Meat sheep and goat

Category of Animal (ewe, goat, replacement, lamb, kid):

Lambs, Goats

Attachment/links:

[HTTPS://WWW.YOUTUBE.COM/WATCH?V=H0L62DWSZJO](https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=H0L62DWSZJO)

Expected Benefits:

- Increased animal welfare
- Increase in profit
- Reduce waste (mainly in feed consumption, for ill-performing animals)
- Better control over your farm
- Improve your genetics by best-performance selection

Costs and Challenges

- The cost of the system varies depending on farm size.
- It comprises a one-time payment for the Smart-Trough devices, a monthly subscription, and ear tags.
- You will need to tag the animals with Trough.AI ear tags for the system to support the individual data collection – the tags are supplied.

This tech works for me because it saves me money by showing me my best/worst performing animals
DAVID, FARMER FROM ISRAEL

